

Functional and Radiological Outcome of Shaft Humerus Fracture Treated By Extension CastRahul Parmar¹, Nitin Popat², Aishwarya Padhiar³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, GMERS Medical College, Porbandar, Gujarat²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopedics, GMERS Medical College, Porbandar, Gujarat³Junior Resident, Department of Microbiology, GMERS Medical College, Porbandar, Gujarat

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Shaft humerus fractures, accounting for 3% of all fractures, are typically caused by falls, sports injuries, or road traffic accidents. While various operative techniques are available, nonoperative methods like extension casting, based on functional bracing principles, are effective and widely practiced. These methods promote fracture healing by preserving the biological environment, offering high union rates with minimal complications.

Material and Methods: This prospective observational study included patients aged 18-65 years with closed shaft humerus fractures (AO/OTA classification 12-A and 12-B), treated using an extension cast under fluoroscopic guidance. Functional and radiological outcomes were assessed using DASH and Constant-Murley scores over a 6-month follow-up, with results statistically analyzed for significance.

Results: Shaft humerus fractures were most common in individuals aged 41-50 years (28%), with a male predominance (64%) and the middle shaft being the most frequently affected region (44%). Clinical, functional, and radiological outcomes varied across age groups, with older patients showing longer union times and slightly reduced composite movements. When outcomes were analyzed by sex, males had better composite shoulder and elbow movements, which were statistically significant, while time to union and angulation showed no significant differences. Based on topographical type, middle shaft fractures demonstrated the shortest time to union and superior composite movements, with statistically significant differences in elbow movement ($p = 0.048$). Morphological comparisons showed no significant differences in union time, but intermediate fractures had better composite shoulder movement ($p = 0.027$), highlighting the influence of fracture characteristics on recovery outcomes.

Conclusion: The shaft humerus fractures treated with extension casts demonstrated favorable clinical, functional, and radiological outcomes, with union rates influenced by age, sex, topographical type, and fracture morphology. Middle shaft fractures and intermediate morphologies showed better overall recovery, emphasizing the importance of individualized treatment approaches.

Keywords: Shaft Humerus Fracture, Extension Cast, Functional Outcomes, Fracture Morphology.

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Introduction

Shaft or diaphyseal fracture of the humerus is defined as extra articular fractures of the humerus excluding 5 cm in each ends. [1] This fracture accounts 3% of all fractures. [2] In last 100 years, various operative techniques developed and successfully used to manage difficult fractures. Initial classifications described are based mainly on the location and to some extent on morphology of the fractures. [3] Subsequently AO classification combined them adequately but, while treating them, biological environments were paid less importance. [1] The causes of diaphyseal fractures are simple fall, fall from height, sports injuries,

road traffic accidents (RTAs) and direct blow. [4] It can be treated by different operative methods using open, dynamic compression or percutaneous helical plates, [5] nails [6] and external fixator. [7] Nonoperative treatment as the definitive method do not interfere the biological environment at the fracture site and provide more chance of union with fewer complications. As the required procedure can be performed in an outpatient department, hospitalization can be avoided. Different nonoperative procedures such as hanging extension cast, U cast and few other methods are successfully employed. But the technique described by

Sarmiento is widely practiced all over the globe. [8] Nonunion with this method of treatment is rare; but when it occurs it involves usually the proximal third shaft humeral fractures. [9] Functional bracing has essentially replaced all other methods of conservative treatment and has become the “gold standard” for non-operative treatment because of its ease of application, adjustability, and allowance of shoulder and elbow motion, relatively low cost and reproducible results. [10]

The humeral functional brace works on the principles of the hydraulic effect of the brace by compressing the soft tissues circumferentially to produce fracture alignment, active contraction of the muscles and beneficial effect of the gravity, and it has been shown to be very effective for treating closed humeral shaft fractures. [8,11] Union rates of 96–100 % have been reported with this technique. [8] A maximum of 3 cm of shortening, 20° anterior or posterior angulation and 30° of varus is acceptable. [12] United fractures with up to this much deformity still allows full functional use of the upper extremity.

Most of the studies state that the average time to union of these fractures is 8–12 weeks. Healing in humeral fractures occurs within the first 3 months in general (average time for union is 8–12 weeks). [11,12] We hypothesized that the extension cast can be made more effective if compression of the cast over arm can be adjusted according to the loss of girth of arm during the course of treatment. More extension of the cast over the shoulder secures further stability at fracture site particularly in more proximal fractures.

Material and Methods

This prospective observational study was conducted at tertiary care hospital, Gujarat over a period of 1 year. The study included patients presenting with shaft humerus fractures who were treated using an extension cast.

The study included patients aged 18-65 years with closed shaft humerus fractures classified under the AO/OTA system as 12-A and 12-B. Patients with pathological fractures, open fractures, neurovascular compromise, or previous humerus surgeries were excluded. A total of 50 patients were enrolled in the study after meeting the

inclusion criteria through a detailed clinical and radiological evaluation. The treatment involved the application of an extension cast under fluoroscopic guidance to ensure proper alignment of the fracture fragments. The cast was positioned with the arm in slight abduction and elbow in extension to maintain the anatomical alignment. Patients were instructed to avoid weight-bearing activities and were followed up for regular monitoring of fracture healing through clinical assessments and radiographs taken at intervals of 4, 8, and 12 weeks.

The functional outcome was evaluated using the Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand (DASH) score and Constant-Murley score at the end of 6 months post-treatment. Radiological outcomes were assessed based on the presence of callus formation, alignment, and union on follow-up X-rays. Complications such as malunion, nonunion, or loss of reduction were also documented.

Data were analyzed using Statistical Software SPSS 21.1. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of patients. Paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were used to compare pre-treatment and post-treatment outcomes. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation or percentage distributions.

Results

In our study, shaft humerus fractures were most prevalent among individuals aged 41-50 years (28%), followed by those aged 31-40 years (22%). Fractures were also observed in younger age groups (21-30 years: 18%, <20 years: 8%) and older age groups (51-60 years: 16%, >60 years: 8%), indicating that this injury can occur across all age ranges.

Male predominance was evident, with 64% of cases being male and 36% female. The middle shaft was the most commonly affected region (44%), followed by the distal shaft (32%) and proximal shaft (24%). Regarding fracture morphology, 40% of cases were classified as simple, while 30% each exhibited complex and intermediate morphologies.

Table 1: Comparison of Clinical, Functional, and Radiological Outcomes Based on Age Distribution

Age Group	Time to Union	Angulation in Coronal Plane	Angulation in Sagittal Plane	Composite Shoulder Movement	Composite Elbow Movement
≤20 (n=4)	9.50 \pm 0.577	7.00 \pm 1.414	6.75 \pm 0.500	91.75 \pm 0.500	96.00 \pm 0.000
21-30 (n=9)	10.00 \pm 0.707	7.33 \pm 1.323	6.00 \pm 0.707	91.78 \pm 0.667	95.78 \pm 0.833
31-40	11.00 \pm 0.775	6.73 \pm 0.905	6.82 \pm 1.168	91.09 \pm 0.701	95.18 \pm 0.751

(n=11)					
41-50 (n=10)	11.50 ± 1.179	6.60 ± 1.174	6.10 ± 1.197	91.10 ± 0.568	95.00 ± 0.471
51-60 (n=3)	11.67 ± 0.577	7.33 ± 0.577	7.00 ± 1.000	90.67 ± 0.577	94.67 ± 0.577
>60 (n=1)	13.00	7.00	5.00	90.00	94.00
P value	<0.001	0.741	0.218	0.016	0.010

In our study, clinical, functional, and radiological outcomes were compared based on sex distribution. The mean time to union was slightly longer in females (11.50 ± 0.926 weeks) compared to males (10.67 ± 1.155 weeks), with a p-value of 0.068, indicating no significant difference. Angulation in the coronal plane was marginally higher in males (7.03 ± 1.129) compared to females (6.50 ± 0.926), while angulation in the sagittal plane was higher in females (7.00 ± 1.195) than in males (6.23 ±

0.971), though neither reached statistical significance (p = 0.228 and 0.067, respectively). Composite shoulder movement was slightly better in males (91.40 ± 0.724) than females (90.75 ± 0.463), with a significant p-value of 0.022. Similarly, composite elbow movement was also better in males (95.43 ± 0.774) than in females (94.75 ± 0.463), with a significant p-value of 0.023. These findings highlight subtle sex-based differences in recovery outcomes.

Table 2: Comparison of Clinical, Functional, and Radiological Outcomes Based on Topographical Type

Topographical Type	Time to Union	Angulation in Coronal Plane	Angulation in Sagittal Plane	Composite Shoulder Movement	Composite Elbow Movement
Distal Shaft (n=10)	11.60 ± 1.174	7.00 ± 1.247	6.00 ± 0.943	90.90 ± 0.738	94.80 ± 0.632
Middle Shaft (n=19)	10.37 ± 0.761	7.05 ± 1.026	6.42 ± 1.071	91.42 ± 0.607	95.53 ± 0.697
Proximal Shaft (n=9)	11.00 ± 1.414	6.56 ± 1.130	6.78 ± 1.093	91.33 ± 0.866	95.33 ± 0.866
P value	0.017	0.530	0.279	0.175	0.048

Clinical, functional, and radiological outcomes were compared based on fracture morphology. Time to union showed no significant difference across groups, with complex fractures averaging 11.21 ± 1.311 weeks, intermediate fractures 10.57 ± 1.158 weeks, and simple fractures 10.70 ± 0.823 weeks (p = 0.311). Composite shoulder movement was significantly better in the intermediate group (91.64 ± 0.633) compared to complex (90.93 ± 0.616) and simple (91.20 ± 0.789) fractures (p = 0.027). Other parameters, including angulation and composite elbow movement, showed no statistically significant differences (p>0.05).

Discussion

Humeral fractures are common and account for 7-8% of all fractures in general population. [13] In our study, shaft humerus fracture was more prevalent in those who belong to fourth to fifth decade of their life (28%) followed by those who had age between 31-40 years. It is found that there is a steep increase in incidence rates in higher age groups. 83% of all humeral fractures occur in patients older than 50 years of age. [14] The population-weighted incidence rate of humeral shaft fracture was 7.22 per 100,000 populations in 2014. Most studies reported a bimodal age distribution of humeral shaft fractures [15,16], while another found that the majority of humeral

shaft fractures occurred among those aged <35 years. [17] A bimodal age-specific distribution has been delineated. [15] There were two peaks in annual incidence rate for humeral shaft fracture, occurring in the third decade, resulting from high-energy trauma, mainly in men, and in the eighth decade, mostly in women with osteoporotic fractures resulting from simple falls. [15] In our study, majority of the patients with shaft humerus fracture were males highlighting the male preponderance (64%) than females (36%). In a study by Kanth et al. [18] reported the majority of patients were males, as they are more prone to road traffic accidents, Male gender was affected more. Our study was comparable with the study of John Meloy et al. [19] 2013, which shows increased prevalence towards the male gender. A study by Ji et al. [20] showed that two peaks occurred, at 5-14 years, mainly in male juveniles, and at 55-64 years in adults, with approximately similar incidences in both sexes. Ji et al. [20] suggested that juveniles of 5-14 years performed considerably more physical activities than younger juveniles (<5 years), and, therefore, were more likely to be exposed to danger. In our study, majority of the patients had middle shaft (44%) affected whereas 32% had distal shaft affected and 24% had proximal shaft affected in present study. According to a study by Bergdahl et al. [14] the highest rate was observed

for proximal fractures (83.0 per 100,000 person-years), followed by shaft and distal fractures (13.4 and 8.3 per 100,000 person-years respectively). An epidemiological study of 401 shaft of humerus fracture found that the mid-shaft was fractured in 43.2% (156), the proximal end in 40.8% (147) and the distal end in 16% (58) of patients. [16] Patients with fractures due to low-energy trauma tended to be older women and those with high-energy fractures most likely to be younger men. Low-energy trauma found to be the most common mechanism of injury in all types of fracture. [15]

Majority of the patients had simple morphology (40%) whereas another 30% each had complex and intermediate morphology. Our finding correlated to the study by Ekholm et al. reported the type-A fractures (simple) by far the most common (220, 61.0%) followed by type-B (wedge; 107, 29.6%) and type-C (complex; 34, 9.4%). In a series of shaft fractures by Bergdahl et al. [14] reported high-energy injuries resulted to a large extent in type A fractures but more seldom in type C fractures compared with low-energy injuries. This differs from what was reported by Tytherleigh-Strong et al. [21] who reported a correlation between high-energy trauma and C fractures. The explanation for the different result might be that our material appears to contain fewer multi-trauma patients, illustrated by a smaller percentage of traffic-related fractures (7.7 % compared with 17.1 %) and open fractures in our material (2.3 %, 5.6 %) and a larger percentage of older women who sustain complex shaft fractures after a simple fall due to the changes in bone quality that constitutes osteoporosis.

We reported on follow up, more than three fourth of the patients had union of fractures (76%) whereas 24% did not have union. In our study, the union was more in patients with either complex (36.8%) or intermediate (36.8%) morphology whereas majority of the patients with simple morphology and non-union (83.3%). Moreover, the union rates were similar across the topographical type as revealed by the insignificant p value of 0.234. Union rate with conservative treatment technique ranges between 77.4% and 100%. [9,22,23]

In a review including almost 2000 patients, Papasoulis et al [9] reported a union rate of 94.5% and a mean time to union of 10.7 weeks. Several studies have shown proximal third humerus fractures treated conservatively had lower union rates than those involving the distal two-thirds. [23,24] Ali et al [24] observed an overall union rate of 83% on a series of 138 fractures of the humeral diaphysis treated with functional bracing. Subgroup analysis showed a lower union rate for the proximal third of 76%, whereas the rates for the middle and distal thirds were 88% and 85% respectively. They also found that oblique fractures

of the proximal third had a lower union rate than other fracture types and locations. Ring et al [22] also found lower union rates for proximal and middle third fractures, and lower union rates for oblique/spiral fractures. It is unclear at this time what the main factor for these differences is; however, a small area of contact between the fragments could explain the lower union rate seen in transverse fractures. For oblique/spiral fractures on the other hand, the reason for this is likely due to incarceration of muscle and soft tissues in the fracture site. Comminuted fractures show a higher union rate than simple fractures regardless of their location. [23] Ekholm et al [16] showed an 82% union rate for type A fractures (according to the AO/OTA classification), [24] while type B and C fractures showed 96% and 100% nonunion rates respectively.

In our study, the union was faster in young patients as compared to older patients ($p < 0.001$), composite shoulder movement were significantly less in old age patients compared to young patients ($p = 0.016$) and similarly composite elbow movement were reduced with increasing age ($p = 0.010$). No significant difference was obtained in terms of angulation in coronal ($p = 0.741$) and sagittal ($p = 0.218$) plane across the age group of patients.

In a retrospective study of 79 patients with conservatively treated humeral shaft fracture, Neuhaus et al [25] observed that smoking, female sex and initial displacement, increase the risk of secondary displacement at six weeks with conservative treatment. [25] in addition, in a retrospective study evaluating union rates after conservative treatment of HSF in elderly patients, Pollock et al [26] found that the incidence of nonunion was significantly higher in patients older than 55 years. Age and oblique fractures of the proximal third are risk factors for nonunion. [27] Surgical indication threshold should be lower in patients older than 55 years presenting with this type of fracture.

We observed that the time to union ($p = 0.068$), angulation in coronal ($p = 0.228$) and sagittal ($p = 0.067$) plane were similar between both the genders whereas Composite shoulder ($p = 0.022$) and elbow ($p = 0.023$) movement were faster in males than females. A study by Papakonstantinou et al. found that there was no association between nonunion and age, sex, mechanism, fracture type, treatment and discharge destination. [28] Another study by Mills et al. [29] reported that The non-union incidence was unimodal in both men and women whereas the fracture incidence was unimodal in women and bimodal in men (although the peak in young men was far smaller than the second one in elderly men), and in both sexes the incidence of fractures was relatively low up to the age of 64 years. [29]

In present study, it was observed that time to union was faster in patients with middle shaft fracture as compared to Proximal Shaft than Distal Shaft. a significant association was obtained between composite shoulder movement with morphological type where composite shoulder movement were higher with intermediate morphology as compared to other two ($p=0.027$). Rest other outcomes such as time to union ($p=0.311$), angulation in coronal plane ($p=0.504$) and angulation in saggital plane ($p=0.985$) were similar across the morphological type. Several studies have shown proximal third humerus fractures treated conservatively had lower union rates than those involving the distal two-thirds. [23,24,30]

Alternatively, several other studies have shown a higher risk of nonunion for transverse fractures. [16,31] It is unclear at this time what the main factor for these differences is; however, a small area of contact between the fragments could explain the lower union rate seen in transverse fractures.

The functional results following treatment with functional bracing appear to be equivalent to that of surgical treatment, thus can be used successfully to manage HSF. [31,32] Papasoulis et al [9] found full range of motion recovery of shoulder and elbow for 80% and 85% of patients respectively. However, it is important to inform patients that the risk of short-term shoulder and elbow stiffness might be higher with bracing.

The primary limitation of our study is the relatively small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the lack of long-term follow-up restricts our ability to assess the durability of outcomes and potential complications over time. Variability in patient adherence to post-treatment rehabilitation protocols may also have influenced the functional outcomes.

Conclusion

The study shows that the extension casting is a safe and efficient alternative that provides results that are as good as the functional brace without restriction of shoulder motion. It also provides comparatively lower incidence of proximal shaft malunion and non-union. The union rate in young, middle shaft fracture, composite and intermediate morphological type fracture patients compared to older, distal and proximal fracture patients.

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